

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

STUDY OF THE PHYSICAL, CHEMICAL, AND ELECTROPHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF ALLOYS OF THE GaSe-TlInSe₂ SYSTEM

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Abstract

Using physicochemical analysis methods (DTA, MCA, X-ray diffraction, as well as microhardness and density determination), the nature of chemical interactions in the GaSe-TlInSe₂ system was studied, and its T-x phase diagram was constructed. The study established that the phase diagram of the GaSe-TlInSe₂ system is quasi-binary and eutectic. The composition of the eutectic formed between GaSe and TlInSe₂ compounds is 70 mol % TlInSe₂, and the temperature is 650°C. In the system at room temperature, 2.5 mol % TlInSe₂ is dissolved in the GaSe compound, and 5 mol % GaSe is dissolved in the TlInSe₂ compound. The temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity and thermoelectric power (EMF) of the (GaSe)_{1-x}(TlInSe₂)_x (x = 0.01; 0.02) solid solution alloys was studied.

Keywords: system, quasi-binary, solid solutions, eutectic, microhardness.

Introduction

Gallium chalcogenides, one of the main elements of subgroup III, as well as new phases and solid solution alloys based on them, are widely used in the electronics industry. Gallium sulfide and selenide compounds are semiconductors with photovoltaic and luminescent properties [1–9].

The compound TlInSe₂ is formed from compounds of TSe and InSe. New phases formed by TlInSe₂ in combination with chalcogenides of other metals also possess functional properties [10–13]. To obtain multicomponent phases with desired properties, it is necessary to study the phase diagrams of the corresponding systems. The phase diagram of the GaSe-TlInSe₂ system was studied for the first time using physicochemical analysis methods.

The aim of this work is to construct a phase diagram for GaSe-TlInSe₂ alloys by physicochemically studying their phase composition and investigating their electrical properties.

Gallium monoselenide GaSe melts congruently at 960°C and crystallizes in a hexagonal system. The lattice parameters are $a = 3.755 \text{ \AA}$; $c = 15.94 \text{ \AA}$, $Z = 4$, space group $P63/mmc = D_{6h}^4$, density $\rho = 5.03 \text{ g/cm}^3$, and microhardness 300 MPa [14]. The compound TlInSe₂ melts at 767°C, density $\rho = 6.90 \text{ g/cm}^3$, and microhardness is 1150 MPa [15].

Experimental part

GaSe-TlInSe₂ alloys were synthesized by co-melting GaSe and TlInSe₂ components in quartz ampoules with air evacuated to a pressure of 0.133 Pa. The alloys were then heat-treated at 650°C for 240 hours to achieve equilibrium. The equilibrium alloys were studied using differential thermal analysis (DTA), microstructural analysis (MSA), and X-ray diffraction (XRD), as well as microstructure and density determination.

DTA analysis of the samples was performed on a THERMOSCAN-2 instrument. The heating rate of the alloys was 5°C/min. X-ray diffraction analysis was per-

formed on a D2 PHASER diffractometer using $CK\alpha$ radiation and a nickel filter. A 1:1 HNO₃ + H₂O₂ solution was used as an abrasive to determine the phase composition of the polished samples. The alloy composition was then examined under an MIM-8 microscope. Microhardness was measured using a PMT-3 metallographic instrument. Density was determined using the pycnometric method, using toluene as the filler solution. The electrical properties of solid solution alloys were measured using the compensation method [16, 17].

Results and discussion

To study the nature of chemical interactions in the GaSe-TlInSe₂ system, alloys of this system were synthesized. The alloys were synthesized by co-melting the GaSe and TlInSe₂ components using the ampoule method. The synthesized alloys are black, compact masses. For the study, the samples were pre-heat treated at 650°C for 300 hours.

The behavior of the resulting alloys under environmental conditions was studied. They were found to be resistant to air, water, and organic solvents. Strong mineral acids (HNO₃, HCl) rapidly decompose them. Homogenized samples were analyzed using physicochemical analysis.

Thermograms of the alloys were recorded in the temperature range of 800–1000°C. Analysis revealed that two endothermic effects are present in the thermograms of the samples. One is related to the solidus of the system, and the other to the liquidus. All samples exhibit isothermal effects at 650°C, which also corresponds to the eutectic temperature.

The microstructure of GaSe-TlInSe₂ alloys containing 2.5, 40, 70, and 95 mol % TlInSe₂ was studied (Fig. 1). As can be seen from Fig. 1, single-phase alloys containing 2.5 and 95 mol % TlInSe₂ are solid solution alloys based on GaSe and TlInSe₂ compounds, respectively. The sample containing 40 mol % TlInSe₂ is biphasic. The alloy containing 70 mol % TlInSe₂ has a eutectic composition.

Fig. 1. Microstructure of alloys of the GaSe-TlInSe₂ system.
1-2.5 mol. %, 2-40 mol. %, 3-70 mol. %, 4-95 mol. % TlInSe₂.

To confirm the results of differential thermal and microstructural analysis, X-ray diffraction patterns of alloys containing 40, 70, and 95 mol. % TlInSe₂ were obtained and compared with the X-ray diffraction patterns of the starting components (Fig. 2). It was found that the diffraction lines of alloys containing 40 and 70 mol. % TlInSe₂ are a mixture of the diffraction lines of the starting components. This indicates a two-phase structure of the alloys of the system containing 40 and

70 mol. % TlInSe₂. In the diffraction pattern, the diffraction lines of the sample containing 95 mol. % TlInSe₂ are similar to the diffraction lines of the TlInSe₂ compound. This means that this sample is a solid solution alloy based on the compound TlInSe₂.

Thus, X-ray diffraction analysis also confirms the quasi-binary nature of the GaSe-TlInSe₂ system.

Fig. 2. Diffractograms of alloys of the GaSe-TlInSe₂ system.
1-GaSe, 2- 40, 3-70, 4-95, 5-100 mol % TlInSe₂.

Based on the results of the studies, a T-x phase diagram of the GaSe-TlInSe₂ system was constructed (Fig. 3). As can be seen from Fig. 3, the phase diagram of the system belongs to the simple eutectic type. For-

mation of a solid solution based on the initial components occurs in a limited region. In the GaSe-based system, a solid solution with a concentration of 2.5 mol. % TlInSe₂ was formed. The area of the solid solution based on the TlInSe₂ compound is 5 mol. % GaSe.

Fig. 3. T - x phase diagram of the GaSe-TlInSe₂ system.

Table 1.

Composition, DTA results, microhardness, and densities of alloys of the GaSe-TlInSe₂ system

Composition, mol %		Thermal efekts, °C	Density, q/cm ³	Microhardness, MPa	
GaSe	TlInSe ₂			α P=0,10 N	β P=0,20 N
100	0,0	960	5,03	300	-
95	5,0	730,950	5,10	350	-
90	10	650,940	5,18	370	-
80	20	650,920	5,42	370	-
70	30	650,890	5,59	370	-
60	40	650,850	5,78	370	-
50	50	650,800	5,96	-	-
40	60	650,725	6,15	-	-
30	70	650	6,33	Eutec.	Eutec.
20	80	650,720	6,53	-	1190
10	90	675,740	6,71	-	1190
5,0	95	720, 760	6,92	-	1180
0,0	100	767	6,90	-	1150

Microhardness measurements of GaSe-TlInSe₂ alloys show that two types of microhardness values have been identified. The compositional dependence of a number of physicochemical properties of this system's alloys is presented in Table 1. As can be seen from the table, the microhardness value (300–370) MPa corresponds to the microhardness of the α -solid solution formed on the basis of GaSe, while the microhardness value (1150–1190) MPa corresponds to the microhardness of the β -solid solution formed on the basis of the TlInSe₂ compound. The dependence of the alloy density on composition is linear and sequential.

The liquidus of the GaSe-TlInSe₂ system consists of a monovariant equilibrium curve of α and β solutions. Alloys in the concentration range of 0–2.5 mol. % and 95–100 mol. % TlInSe₂ in this region are single-phase. In the concentration range of 2.5–95 mol. %

TlInSe₂, two-phase alloys consisting of ($\alpha + \beta$) crystallize below the solidus line. Co-crystallization of GaSe and TlInSe₂ compounds in this system ends with the formation of a binary eutectic of 70 mol. % TlInSe₂ composition with a melting point of 650°C.

To study the temperature dependence of electrical conductivity and thermo-EMF of alloys of solid solutions (GaSe)_{1-x}(TlInSe₂)_x ($x=0.01; 0.02$), samples with a concentration of 1 and 2 mol. % TlInSe₂ were subjected to heat treatment at a temperature of 600°C for 100 h. The samples had the shape of a parallelepiped with dimensions of 1.4 x 0.8 x 1.0 cm. Physical measurements were carried out in the temperature range of 300–600 K. Figure 4 shows the temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity of samples with a concentration of 1 and 2 mol. % TlInSe₂.

Fig. 4. Temperature dependence of electrical conductivity of solid solution alloys $(\text{GaSe})_{1-x}(\text{TIInSe}_2)_x$ ($x = 0.01; 0.02$). 1-1 mol. %, 2-2 mol. % TIInSe_2 .

As can be seen from the graph in figure 4, the electrical conductivity of alloys containing 1 and 2 mol. % TIInSe_2 increases with temperature and composition. For both samples, impurity conductivity manifests itself in the temperature range of 300–430 K. Beginning

at 430 K, intrinsic conductivity emerges. As a result, electrical conductivity increases sharply with temperature. This indicates that alloys containing 1 and 2 mol.% TIInSe_2 have semiconductor properties.

Fig. 5. Temperature dependence of thermo-EMF of solid solution alloys $(\text{GaSe})_{1-x}(\text{TIInSe}_2)_x$ ($x = 0.01; 0.02$). 1-1 mol. %, 2-2 mol. % TIInSe_2 .

Figure 5 shows the temperature dependence of the thermo-EMF of GaSe-TIInSe_2 alloys. The thermo-EMF of alloys containing 1 and 2 mol.% TIInSe_2 increases with temperature and reaches a maximum value at 440 K. With a further increase in temperature, the thermo-EMF begins to decrease.

Conclusion

Thus, the T-x phase diagram of the GaSe-TIInSe_2 system has been constructed, and it has been established that the phase diagram is quasi-binary and eutectic. At room temperature, the system has a solubility of 2.5 mol. % TIInSe_2 calculated as GaSe and 5 mol %

GaSe calculated as TIInSe_2 . The composition of the binary eutectic formed in the system is 70 mol. % TIInSe_2 , and its melting point is 650°C . The microhardness and density of the system's alloys were studied as functions of composition. The temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity and thermo-EMF of the $(\text{GaSe})_{1-x}(\text{TIInSe}_2)_x$ ($x = 0.01; 0.02$) solid solution alloys was studied. It was established that the solid solution alloys are semiconductors with medium resistance.

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